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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date

Unit name	
Country	
Number of researchers	
Number of students	
Link to the website	
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	

Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

Yes

No

If so:

1.	What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?
2.	What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?
3.	What are the basic assessment criteria?

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4.	Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?
5.	How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?
6.	Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?
7.	Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?
8.	Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?
9.	Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?
10.	Does the assessment of scientific achievements consider bibliometric indicators??
11.	Do the assessment criteria consider elements considered as Open Science?
12.	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)

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13.	<p>Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?</p>
14.	<p>Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?</p>
15.	<p>Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?</p>

If no:

1.	<p>What does the assessment process for researchers look like?</p>
2.	<p>What are the assessment rules?</p>
3.	<p>Despite the lack of a formal system, do researchers know the principles of assessment?</p>
4.	<p>Are there any consequences after the assessment of academic staff are completed, and if so, what are they?</p>
5.	<p>Do you intend to implement a formal system for assessing scientists in the future?</p>

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